

Ho Chi Minh's Thought on Democracy and Promoting Democratic Right Today in Vietnam

Assoc. Prof, Dr. Pham Ngoc Tram¹, MSc. Vo Hong An²

¹Thu Dau Mot University (TDMU), Binh Duong, Vietnam

²Strong Research Group "History & Culture" of Thu Dau Mot University (TDMU), Binh Duong, Vietnam

ABSTRACT: Democracy plays an especially important role in the history of thought, because it is not only the primary mode for establishing a good, humane society for human happiness; but also the driving force to promote the socio-economic development of each country and nation. Therefore, most countries in the world, including Vietnam, consider democracy as the goal of their development strategy. Ho Chi Minh left our Party and our people an invaluable legacy of theoretical arguments on particularly important issues of the Vietnamese revolution, including philosophical profound thoughts on democracy, which until now, it still has theoretical and practical value.

KEYWORDS: Democracy, Communist Party of Vietnam, Ho Chi Minh

INTRODUCTION

One of the issues of great significance in Ho Chi Minh's ideological heritage is democracy. Ho Chi Minh's thought on democracy is expressed with rich, vivid and profound content. It is both the crystallization of the national culture, the quintessence of human culture, and the vivid realization of the Vietnamese revolution as well as the features of the era. Ho Chi Minh's thought on democracy was not only the theoretical basis and guideline but also the methodological basis for the cause of the Vietnamese revolution under the leadership of the Party in the struggle for national liberation. as in the current country building and renovation career. The article contributes to clarify Ho Chi Minh's thoughts on democracy and the current application of the Communist Party of Vietnam.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ho Chi Minh's thoughts on democracy and promoting the people's ownership

Ho Chi Minh's thought on democracy is the result of the deep understanding of the role of the people in history: "People are the most precious, the most important, the ultimate", "There are no What is as precious as the people. There is nothing as strong in the world as the united force of the people" (Ho, 2000e: 276); "People are the roots of the country, of the revolution", "Revolution is the cause of the masses", "People are unanimous, anything can be done. The people do not support, they should not do anything" (Ho, 2000e: 293); "The country is based on the people. Stump has a new sustainable tree. Build a successful building based on the people" (Ho, 2000e: 409-410). He mobilized the strength of the entire people in the struggle for self-liberation, greatly contributed to bringing the Vietnamese people to independence and freedom, bringing our people from slavery to the status of national mastery, control of society. Therefore, "I do not do anything against the people with regard to the people". President Ho Chi Minh is well aware of the role of democracy, considering democracy as the driving force for development; practicing democracy is the universal key to solving all difficulties.

President Ho Chi Minh affirmed that democracy means democracy is democracy and democracy is ownership. The person who pointed out, the people's status is the owner towards society, the country and the people are the subjects of power. This is the core content of Ho Chi Minh's democratic ideology, reflecting the highest and most common value of democracy is the power belonging to the people: "Our country is a democratic country, the highest status is the people, because democracy is democracy" (Ho, 2000c: 515), "our regime is a democracy, that is, the people are the masters" (Ho, 2000f: 572). This affirms the real social value of democracy in that it is to give the majority of the working people their own powers through the struggle to reform the old society and build a new society of their own the masses of the people. President Ho Chi Minh had only one "ultimate desire and desire to make the country independent, the people free, everyone had meals, clothes, and education". He has strived tirelessly, doing everything to realize Independence - Freedom - Happiness for the Fatherland, the people and the people. He has drawn a truth not only for the nation but also for humanity "nothing is more precious than independence and freedom".

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Infused with Marxist-Leninist views, President Ho Chi Minh especially emphasized the need to build a democratic regime, a political institution and a democratic state institution, a state of the people, a state of the people and for the people. "How many benefits are for the people, "he affirmed. How many powers are of the people. Renovation work, construction is the responsibility of the people. The cause of the resistance war and national construction is the work of the people. The government from the commune to the central government is elected by the people. The mass organizations from the central to the commune are organized by the people. In short, power and power are in the people" (Ho, 2000d: 515). Our state is a state of the people; consider the people as powerful subjects; The state is a tool of the people, a form to gather and gather the strength of the entire nation into a common cause, but the state is not a place for "promotion, prosperity", sharing power and benefits.

After the home country won its independence, in the first session of the revolutionary Government of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam, he requested to hold the General Election as soon as possible with universal suffrage. A state is run by the people, ie the people must participate in the affairs of the state. Although the National Assembly of our country is in the highest position, it is not a centralized agency with all power. When there appear to be jobs related to the country's destiny, it will be given to the entire people. The State is by the people in Ho Chi Minh's thought that the people do themselves, take care of their jobs by themselves, through relationships in society, through mass organizations, not the state subsidizing, replacing the people, making people enjoy moving, relying on, waiting. The state for the people, that is, our state has no other interests besides serving the people, that is the working class nature of our State. The person who requests all the works of the State must clearly show that nature: "Whatever works for the people, we must do our best. Whatever harm is done to the people, we must do our best to avoid" (Ho, 2000c: 698-700). He reminded the authorities at all levels to avoid mistakes, shortcomings, bad habits, diseases that easily infect state power agencies such as: trust, corruption, self-indulgence, divided, arrogant...

President Ho Chi Minh requested that all undertakings, policies and regulations of the State from the central to local levels come from the interests of the people. All State officials are for the people, wholeheartedly serving the people, performing industriously, with integrity, righteousness, and impartiality. A state for the people must ensure that the people have a prosperous and happy life. He clearly pointed out the responsibilities and obligations of the Party and State to the people. "If the people are hungry, the Party and Government are at fault; if the people are cold, the Party and the Government are at fault; if the ignorant people are the Party and the Government is at fault". The State not only knows how to benefit the people, but also respects the people. He reminded us that we must love the people, and respect the people, the people will love me and me; At the same time, it is necessary to make people understand clearly: "If the people have an interest in ownership, they have the obligation to fulfill their citizenship and keep the civic morality" (Ho, 2000c: 409-410).

In Ho Chi Minh's thought, the state of the people, by the people, for the people must be a powerful rule-of-law state, governed by law and must make the law into effect in practice. In a democratic state, democracy and the law must always go hand in hand and have a close relationship to ensure a strong government. There can be no democracy outside of the law, the law is the midwife of democracy. All democratic rights of the people must be institutionalized by the constitution and law, on the contrary, the legal system must ensure that the people's freedom and democracy are respected in practice. Building a socialist legal system to ensure the exercise of the people's power is the lifelong concern of President Ho Chi Minh. Besides, he also pointed out the relationship between dictatorship and democracy: "Every regime has a dictatorship, the question of who is authoritarian to whom?... Like a treasure box, there must be a lock. The house must have a door... Democracy is the most precious treasure of the people, the main is the key, the door to guard against spoilers... Then democracy also needs to have a dictatorship to preserve democracy" (Ho, 2000f: 279)

Ho Chi Minh always determined that democracy is the driving force of social progress and development. The democracy that we are trying to build is the democracy of the vast majority of the people, associated with social justice and progress in every step of development and each development policy. Uncle Ho once said: to lead a country that allows our people to be backward and to be disadvantaged in enjoying human happiness is also a loss of democracy. Ownership is the people's divine right that no one can invade. President Ho Chi Minh emphasized that the responsibility of the Party and State in promoting the people's mastery is to make them capable of mastering, enjoying, using democratic rights, dare to say and dare to do. To promote democracy is to promote the talents of the people. If we want to do so, we must "respect the people, be close to the people, understand the people, learn the people and be responsible to the people". According to Uncle: "Without studying the people, we cannot lead the people. Only know how to be a local student, and can be a teacher of a local student".

Respect for the people, trust the people, learn the people, organize and educate to bring into full play the power of the people is consistent throughout the entire career of President Ho Chi Minh's revolutionary activities. He affirmed: believe in the people, bring all problems to the people to discuss and find solutions. We have defects, then honestly admit it in front of the people. Any resolution that people think is not appropriate, then let them propose repairing. According to President Ho Chi Minh, before doing anything, the Party and government also have to discuss with the people, ask for their opinions and experiences, together with them to make plans to suit the local circumstances and then motivate and organize them to act. During the implementation, it is necessary to monitor, help urge and encourage the people; After completing the implementation, we must accompany them to review the work, learn from experience, criticize, and reward. In the process of building socialism, our Party, State and people

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have step by step created the economic, political and social basis of the socialist democracy; people's social power is defined in the Constitution and law; the people's need for democracy is increasingly developing; The people's awareness and capacity to practice democracy are increasingly enhanced ...

Applying Ho Chi Minh's ideology on democracy, promoting the people's mastery of Communist Party of Vietnam

In the process of leading the revolution, the throughout viewpoint of our Party is: "Socialist democracy is the essence of our regime, which is both the goal and the driving force for the development of the country" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2011: 84-85). To meet the requirement of democratic expansion, our Party and State have issued many undertakings and policies to promote people's mastery.

The 6th Congress of the Party started the renovation work outlined the motto "People know, people discuss, people do, people check" and summarized lessons learned: "In all its activities, the Party must contemplate thoroughly the thought of "taking the people as the root", building and promoting the right to mastery of the people working".

The Party's Congress VII required to organize and mobilize all classes of people to actively participate in building laws and policies, and contribute opinions to state agencies at all levels to build regulations and regulations. The convention is in accordance with the laws and undertakings and policies of the State, participates in the popularization of laws among the people and organizes mass movements to implement the laws and policies of the State.

The 8th Congress of the Party defines the task of building a mechanism to implement the motto "People know, people discuss, people do, people check" for the undertakings and policies of the Party and State; well implement the people's mastery mechanism through elected bodies, direct ownership in the form of self-governance, ensure democracy in decision-making and decision-making.

The Ninth Party Congress stated: "Well implement the democratic regulations, expand direct democracy at the grassroots level, create conditions for people to participate in social management, discuss and decide on important issues. important. Overcoming all manifestation of formal democracy. Building the Law on Referendum".

The 10th Party Congress has determined: "All the Party's lines and policies and the laws of the State are for the benefit of the people, with the participation of the people".

The country building platform in the period of transition to socialism (addition and development in 2011), our Party once again affirmed: "The cause of the revolution is for the people, by the people, for the people. It is the people who make the historic victories. All activities of the Party must come from the legitimate interests and aspirations of the people. The Party's strength is its close attachment to the people. Bureaucracy, orders, and distance from the people will lead to immeasurable losses to the destiny of the country, of the socialist regime and of the Party", "Our State is a social rule-of-law State the meaning of the people, by the people, for the people", "The State serves the people, closely attaches to the people, fully realizes the people's democratic rights, respects and listens to the opinions of the people. the people and subject to the people's supervision; adopt mechanisms and measures to control, prevent and punish bureaucracy, corruption, waste, irresponsibility, abuse of power, and violation of citizens' democratic rights; keep strictly disciplined.

Resolution of the XII Congress of the Party continued to state: "Continuing to promote socialist democracy, ensuring all state power belongs to the people. All lines and undertakings of the Party, policies and laws of the State must derive from the aspirations, legitimate rights and interests of the people, and be consulted by the people. Democracy must be implemented fully and seriously in all areas of social life. Ensure people are involved in all stages of decision-making processes regarding benefits, from initiating initiatives, participating in discussions and debating to monitoring implementation. Focus on building legal documents directly related to the people's ownership" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016: 169), "Institutionalize and well implement the motto "People know, people discuss, people" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016: 170).

The socialist democracy and the guarantee of promoting socialist democracy in our country today are not only confirmed in the Party's policies and lines, but also institutionalized and guaranteed through The Constitution and legal system of the State. In terms of building and perfecting institutions, policies and laws on the implementation of democracy, the XII Congress assessed: "The Party and State continue to issue many guidelines, policies and laws to promote democracy socialist, ensuring the exercise of the people's mastery. Human rights, basic rights and obligations of citizens are more fully defined in the 2013 Constitution and in the newly enacted and revised legal system. Clearly affirming human rights, political, civil, economic, cultural and social rights that are recognized, respected, protected and guaranteed under the Constitution and law; Communist Party of Vietnam, 2016: 167) associated civil rights with obligations and responsibilities to the society.

A living proof for the above assessment of the Party is the constitutional principle of practice and promotion of democracy recognized in the 2013 Constitution, such as: "1. The State of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam is a socialist rule-of-law state of the People, by the People, for the People; 2. The Socialist Republic of Vietnam is owned by the People; all state power belongs to the People whose foundation is the alliance between the working class with the peasant class and the intellectual contingent" (Article 2); "The State guarantees and promotes the mastery of the people. people; recognizing, respecting, protecting and ensuring human rights and citizen's rights; realizing the goal of a rich people, a strong country, a democracy, equality and

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civilization, everyone has a prosperous, free, happy life, with comprehensive development conditions" (Article 3); "The people exercise state power through direct democracy, by democracy representing through the National Assembly, the People's Council and through other State organs" (Article 6) ... Democratic rights People's rights are also recorded in Chapter II of the 2013 Constitution (provisions on human rights, basic rights and obligations of citizens) as well as in many other legal documents, such as the Law on promulgation of documents legal normative documents, Law on referendum, Land Law, Criminal Procedure Code, Civil Procedure Code, Law on Organization of the National Assembly, Law on Government Organization, Law on Organization of Local Government, Law on Access to Information, Law on Press, Law on Dissemination, Law Education, Labor Code, Law on Health Insurance...

Practice of direct democracy through the Democracy Regulation at grassroots recently

While we attach great importance to promoting democracy at the central level, where the macro-policies and policies are formulated, we must strive to embrace democracy at the grassroots level, because the grassroots are on duty. continue to implement all undertakings and policies of the Party and State, where exercising the people's rights in the most direct and widespread way. Over the past time, stemming from the requirements and demands of reality after the events that happened in Thai Binh and some localities due to the shortcomings in the practice and promotion of democracy at grassroots since the late 1990s. Last century, the Politburo issued Directive No. 30-CT / TW, dated 18/02/1998, on the establishment and implementation of the democratic regulations at grassroots level. This is a major policy of the Party, extremely important in building and promoting the people's mastery, creating a strong driving force to promote the construction and defense of the Fatherland, and this is also This is the first time our Party has issued a separate document to lead and direct the concretization of the guideline "People know, people discuss, people do, people check", marked a change in awareness of democracy and socialist practice, expressing 5 basic points of view on the construction and implementation of regulations. Democracy at the grassroots level, up to now, still has its value: The promotion of the people's mastery must be placed in the overall mechanism of the political system "The Party leads, the State manages, the people take ownership. "To bring into play well the representative democracy, improve the quality and effectiveness of activities of the National Assembly, the Government, People's Councils and People's Committees at all levels, and well implement the direct democracy regime continue at the grassroots level so that people can discuss and decide directly on important and practical jobs associated with their interests knowledge, creating conditions for the expansion of democracy with quality and efficiency Democracy must go hand in hand with discipline and order; powers associated with responsibilities and interests go hand in hand with obligations.

Institutionalizing the undertakings and views of Directive No. 30-CT / TW, State agencies have issued many legal documents to promote the implementation of democracy at grassroots: Standing Committee of the National Assembly. The Association issued many resolutions, conclusions and in 2007 issued Ordinance No. 34/2007 / PL-UBTVQH11 on the implementation of democracy in communes, wards and towns; The Government has issued, supplemented, amended, and replaced many decrees on the regulations on the implementation of democracy in various grassroots, and is currently implementing Decree No. 149 (2018) on the grassroots democracy at workplaces (enterprises) and Decree No. 04 (2015) on implementing democracy in the operation of state administrative agencies and public non-business units. These are important legal documents that are in effect, contributing to the content and views of our Party on the practice and promotion of democracy, building and implementing the democratic regulations at the grassroots level come to life.

Implementing the Party's directives and conclusions and the State's legal documents, in recent years, especially in recent years, the implementation of the Grassroots Democracy Regulation has seen many positive changes. Increasingly awareness of democracy and the practice of democracy by the Party committees, authorities, the Fatherland Front, socio-political organizations, officials, party members, civil servants, public employees and all walks of life raised. Administrative reform, especially administrative procedure reform, has undergone many changes. Dialogue, citizen reception, complaint handling, denunciation and legitimate and legitimate proposals and aspirations of people and businesses are more concerned than before. The spirit and attitude of serving the people and ethics of public service of the contingent of cadres, civil servants and public employees have made many progress. People's inspection boards, investment supervision boards of communities, conciliation teams at grassroots levels have operated quite effectively, promoting people's direct democracy in residential areas. Social supervision and criticism activities, suggestions for Party building, administration of the Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations have achieved many results, some places have organized social criticism activities. associations at district and grassroots levels. The people participated more actively in the work of building and regulating the Party and building the government. Ownership of the people, forms of representative democracy were promoted, direct democracy expanded; The motto "People know, people discuss, people do, people check" are concretized in many fields of social life.

The implementation of the Regulation on democracy at the grassroots level has contributed to promoting the role, potential and creativity of the people in discussing the affairs of the locality and the country; to give opinions on building policies, laws, regulations, conventions, to build the Party and the administration, to participate in monitoring the activities of cadres, civil servants and party members in residential areas. The democratic atmosphere in the Party and in society is more open. Many

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difficulties in the development process have been discussed, removed and solved effectively, such as: Compensation, support and resettlement when land acquisition is implemented to implement works and projects; land donation for construction works, land consolidation, land exchange, environmental sanitation, new rural construction, civilized urban areas; building solidarity collectives, successfully completing political and professional tasks in administrative agencies and non-business units; improving techniques, increasing labor productivity in enterprises... creating an excited atmosphere, encouraging all classes of people to step up emulation movements, contributing to helping our country overcome difficulties, gaining great achievements in socio-economic development and improvement. and improve people's lives; ensuring national defense and security; building a clean and strong Party, government and political system; creating consensus in society, strengthening the block of great solidarity for the entire people, strengthening the close relationship between the Party, the State and the people; improve the position of our country in the international arena.

The above results are attributed to the leadership, direction and implementation of the Party Committees, authorities, the Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations; promote propaganda, grasp thoroughly and organize the implementation of the Party's guidelines, the State's laws on the building and implementation of the democratic regulations at the grassroots level; all walks of life agreed to support, respond and actively participate. In particular, the Central Steering Committee has implemented the Democracy Regulation at the grassroots level and the steering committees at all levels have made great efforts, actively working, upholding the responsibility of advising the Party committees in leadership work, producer; strengthen inspection, guide, and exchange of experiences in clusters and areas to replicate good models, effective methods, rectify and rectify misleading and weak manifestations.

In addition to the achieved results, it is also necessary to frankly point out the shortcomings and weaknesses such as: Propaganda, dissemination and grasping the Party's policies, the State's laws on the implementation of the democratic regulations in some localities, agencies and units were not timely; Many places of implementation are still formalistic and coping. The disclosure of relevant contents in many localities and institutions is not sufficient, and has not created favorable conditions for people to access information. The promotion of the people's roles and responsibilities to participate in discussing and deciding local issues, and to supervise and contribute to the building of the Party and government in some places is still limited. The implementation of democratic regulations in all types of enterprises, especially non-state enterprises and private sector enterprises, still faces many difficulties; Sometimes, in some places, there are still cases of violations of democracy, causing frustration, complaints against people and over-level, but the settlement has not been thoroughly resolved, especially in the implementation of policies and laws on land, compensation and re-settlement. Settlement when land acquisition. It is not timely to grasp the situation of the people and handle organizations and individuals that violate the people's ownership rights. The role of the Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations in propaganda, mobilization, mass gathering, and promotion of the general strength of the masses remains inadequate. There is still a situation in which a part of the people take advantage of democracy to demand, claim improperly, improperly with the law, disregard discipline, water permission, even being taken advantage of by hostile forces, manipulating greed. demonstrators, disruptive, gather large numbers of people, lose security, social order and safety, violate the law.

Some solutions to promote direct democracy in the coming time

Reality shows that implementing democracy regulations at the grassroots level and promoting the people's ownership role is the decisive factor in creating social consensus. In the countryside, when democracy is promoted, each family, each person is discussed and understood to perform the common work well, the village's friendship is firmly attached, sharing and helping each other in life. daily. In the neighborhood, promoting democracy well, people participating in the constitutional contribution, together building a cultural and friendly living environment, there will be civilized neighborhoods. In each agency, unit, where democracy is well promoted, there will surely be a united, unified team, successfully completing political and professional tasks, each member of the collective is attached, share. In each enterprise, when a democratic atmosphere is aroused, business owners can listen to employees' thoughts, aspirations, and proposals, sympathy and sharing, and will form collective labor teams creative, know the commitment and hardship, overcome difficulties together, create productivity, quality, labor efficiency many times higher... And vice versa, where there is lack of democracy, only imposition and orders, that place will lack vitality, in terms of dissatisfaction, disunity, factions, the work cannot be highly effective. Therefore, the Party committees, authorities, the Fatherland Front and mass organizations need to continue to thoroughly grasp, fully and comprehensively realize the Party's guiding views and State laws on implementation. democracy; strengthening leadership, directing the building and implementation of democratic regulations in each locality, agency and unit to ensure the nature and efficiency; where it has done well, it is necessary to maintain and do better, where it is not good or does not meet the requirements, it is necessary to urge, rectify, and help the implementation to get better; how to make the implementation of democratic regulations and promote democracy become a human factor, the driving force for socio-economic development, take better care of the people's lives, interests and happiness, implement social justice, live with culture, gratitude, ensure security and social security, create a driving force for revolutionary action movements of the masses, participate in the development of the country in general and each geographical areas, agencies and units in particular.

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A decisive factor to the quality and effectiveness of the formulation and implementation of democratic regulations is the role of the heads of the party committees, authorities at all levels and agencies and units. Each comrade secretary at all levels, from Central Commissioners to grassroots commissars, key leaders of state agencies, governments at all levels, agencies and units must promote democracy in the Party, openly and transparently in the administration of the government, truly uphold the role of accountability, pioneer role, role model, anti-bureaucracy, authoritarianism, corruption, waste and acts of aggression. violating the people's ownership rights; regularly consolidate, consolidate and arrange qualified and qualified staff to be in charge of the Steering Committee for the implementation of the democratic regulations. Where the party committee, the party organization, the exemplary head, cares about the leadership, creates conditions for the Steering Committee to operate and promote its role well, the implementation of the democratic regulations has a background sticky, real and comprehensive changes, widely to each locality, agency, unit, enterprise.

The country is increasingly developing, setting up the need to step up theoretical research, summarize the practice of promoting socialist democracy and implementing the democratic regulations at the grassroots level. On the basis of the Party, National Assembly's, People's Councils' line and views, the People's Councils at all levels should continue to improve operational efficiency and better implement the representative democracy; intensifying the review and institutionalization of the Party's guidelines, supplementing, amending and promulgating the system of legal documents in order to promote the people's mastery. For policies and laws that have direct relation to people's lives, it is necessary to listen to people's opinions before making decisions; "People know, people discuss, people do, people check and supervise" must become the motto to mobilize the masses, ensuring that all policies and laws must come from legitimate and legitimate interests and aspirations of people.

State administrative agencies and governments at all levels need to continue improving the effectiveness and efficiency of state management, ensuring effective implementation of policies and laws; to focus on directing and administering socio-economic development goals, constantly improving the material and spiritual life of all classes of people, well implementing social welfare policies; promote administrative reform, create favorable conditions for people to carry out administrative procedures; seriously implementing citizen reception, strengthening dialogue, paying attention to solving people's legitimate and legitimate petitions and aspirations, solving complaints and denunciations, not letting hot spots arise. , the case is complicated and prolonged; improve public service ethics, the quality of service for the people of the contingent of cadres, civil servants and public employees; build a government that is really friendly, close to the people and for the people.

The Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations need to perform well the role of social supervision and criticism, especially issues directly related to the rights and interests of the people; functional agencies, the Steering Committee for the implementation of democratic regulations, the Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations need to continue promoting information, propaganda and awareness raising for all strata of the people. on the Party's undertakings and lines, the State's policies and laws; propaganda about the purpose, meaning and importance of the implementation of the democratic regulations at the grassroots level, helping people to see their rights, self-discipline to fulfill their responsibilities, citizenship and democratic rights directly under the law; Even in cases where the policies and laws are correct but people do not understand or agree, they must make efforts to propagate, explain and promptly adjust policies and laws to suit the reality of life. Focusing on propaganda and broad recognition of good examples and good models on building and implementing the democratic regulations at grassroots level, making the practice of democracy more and more penetrate into all rich and diverse activities of facility life.

Democracy is both a common value of humanity, class, historical, at the same time bearing traditional marks, national characteristics and epochal characteristics. In each country, the level of democracy in society depends largely on the level of social development, the intellectual level of the people, the powers and capacity to exercise ownership of all strata of the people; No country has the right to impose its democratic concepts and content on other nations. Therefore, in parallel with promoting and expanding democracy, it must be associated with strict discipline and discipline; to uphold the responsibility of the society and the population community; resolutely fight with conspiracies and tricks to take advantage of the guise of "democracy", "human rights", distort national and religious issues to interfere in the internal affairs of our country.

CONCLUSION

The more social development, the more democratic content as well as the realization of democracy come into reality. In the present conditions, it can be said that Ho Chi Minh's thought on democracy is the foundation, the theoretical basis for the completion of the political system, the building of the rule of law, and the creation of a democratic mechanism increasingly perfect in our country. In other words, President Ho Chi Minh's thoughts on democracy are an extremely precious legacy and the task of the entire Party and the people is to make these values a reality in order to promote human mastery, promote the legal, social discipline and the block of great national solidarity.

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